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Digital Competency : An analysis of Self efficacy and Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Embracing online teaching methodology

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to explore the acceptance of new teaching methodology of online teaching mode by teachers . Since online teaching has become inevitable in the current pandemic scenario the study aims to understand the self- efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers as they adopt themselves to the new norm. Digital competencies of teachers were assed based on certain parameters while trying to understand the self- efficacy beliefs of the teachers in accepting and aligning themselves as per the new requirements. The study uses structured questionnaire which was distributed among 260 teachers working in undergraduate colleges of Navi Mumbai region. The aim of the study was to understand the self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers with reference to online teaching which has become imminent in the post pandemic scenario.

KEYWORDS : Digital competency, Online teaching, Self efficacy, Job Satisfaction, Technology acceptance model.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Digital competence is the set of skills, knowledge and attitudes that enable the effective, efficient and critical use of technologies and systems. The COVID-19 pandemic situation has brought in inevitable situations in education sector requiring teachers to adapt to teaching online. A conventional classroom system with formal classes was replaced by remote teaching through online platforms. Students were required to listen to their teachers, work individually or in groups, and predominantly reproduce knowledge in assessments (e.g., Lipowsky 2015). Now ICT platforms are to be used by teachers, students as a new approach to learning and development. Teacher education opportunities to learn digital competence, are instrumental in adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closures (Daniela, Biela, Glutsch 2020). Teachers and students learned to use new IT platforms such as Microsoft teams, Google hangouts, Zoom as a new system of education. There are a number of challenges to adapt to this change. Engaging students and indulging them in teaching-learning progression is yet another stumbling block in adoption of online teaching. Teacher's attitude to acquire digital competence and accepting the change in a positive way played vital role to assimilate the learners into new teaching mode.

Self-efficacy refers to beliefs about one's capabilities to learn or perform behaviors at designated levels. A person's belief in his or her capability and a strong determination to enhance performance is known as self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is defined as individualist beliefs and judgments of their capabilities to manage and execute necessary changes for positive outcomes (Bandura, 1997) As per research self-efficacy plays an important role in achievement contexts and outcomes of achievement-related actions (Shunck, Pagares 2002). This concept has been widely researched in the field of education and it is important aspect in a teacher which play a wide role in influencing students attainments and behavior (Tschannen Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001).

Professional aspirations and the respect perceived by teachers depends on their self efficacy and accordingly they are satisfied with profession (Imants & Van Zoelen, 1995). Self efficacy of teachers also depends on their aspirations , respect they perceive and motivational factors (Woolfolk Hoy & Davis, 2006). A strong sense of teacher's self-efficacy promotes collaborative learning environment and good interpersonal relations with colleagues and parents (Coladarci, 1992), A person's self-efficacy is a strong determinant of their effort, persistence, strategizing, as well as their subsequent training and job performance. Besides being highly predictive, self-efficacy can also be developed in order to harness its performance enhancing benefits.

Job satisfaction: Job satisfaction is affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying (Vroom, 1964). Job satisfaction is a worker's sense of achievement and success on the job. It is generally perceived to be directly linked to productivity as well as to personal well-being. Job satisfaction implies doing a job one enjoys, doing it well and being rewarded for one's efforts (Kaliski,2007). The positive relationships to technological change include improvement of task significance, salary increase, improvement of the quality of supervision, improved co-workers relations and increase benefits (Islam,2003). Advances and developments in technology have impacted every sector. Innovations in technology can change the way business activities are performed, helps to reduce costs, improve operations, enhance customer service, and improve communications. Employees can make or break an organization (Deal, 2007); they are considered valuable assets to the corporation organization. IT adoption and job satisfaction has been tapped by many researchers within the construction industry and from different perspectives. Understanding the advancements of IT and adoption of it by employees not only to perform and also helps to increase organizational productivity (Igbaria and Tan, 1997).

The pandemic situations has made every sector including the education sector to adopt new technological applications to survive in business environments. Previous research has also found that teachers' sense of efficacy is related to their satisfaction with their choice of profession and their competence (Trentham, Silvern, & Brogdon, 1985). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs have a crucial role in affecting and sustaining their commitment to school and their job satisfaction. The present study aims to understand how efficiently the teachers raised their digital competency levels with their positive attitude and beliefs to fit into the same role with change in environmental settings.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY & FINDINGS

The conceptual framework has been framed for the research work the representation of which is figure 1. The digital competence of teachers has been measured based on the Variables defined Ease of Use (EU), Utility (U) , Perceived beliefs (PB), Student involvement (SI) which imply the self-efficacy beliefs and job satisfaction of the teachers.

Figure 1

Primary survey has been done with the help of questionnaire and the respondents of the study are teachers working in undergraduate colleges. 260 Respondents data was found to be valid based on which the data has been analyzed. Sample descriptive statistics of the respondent’s demographic data are tabulated in Table 1. A five-point Likert scale was used to collect the responses. The reliability of each construct was examined using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. All the items were found to be above the acceptance level.

Table 1- Frequency distribution of teacher’s demographic information

Gender	N	Percent
Male	49	18.7
Female	211	81.3
Age	N	Percent
Below 25 years	8	2.9
25-34 years	81	31.2
35-44 years	87	33.5
45 –54 years	64	24.7
Above 55 years	20	7.7

Questionnaire was developed to understand the digital competence of teachers based on certain constructs which measured the self-efficacy beliefs and Job Satisfaction of teachers. Table 2 defines the constructs used and the questionnaire items included.

Table 2 : Constructs and questionnaire items included

Variable/ Construct	Scaled Variable	Questionnaire Items
Ease of Use	EU	EU1 - I am able to learn and adapt myself to online teaching methods Easily. EU2 - Using online technology is helping me improve my teaching Effectiveness.
Utility	U	U1 :Online teaching tools help me share more informative and practical resources than traditional classroom method.
Perceived benefits	PB	PB1: Online teaching gives me more flexibility in managing my things PB2: With online teaching am more organized in my teaching Methodology.
Student Involvement	SI	SI1: I am capable to handle all the challenges I encounter while teaching online without much difficulty.
Self- Efficacy beliefs	SE	SE1: Am able to positively engage even the most difficult students in online teaching.
Job Satisfaction	JS	JS1: In all using online technology in my job is Positive and beneficial JS2: Overall am satisfied with my job with online teaching mode.

A five-point Likert scale was used to collect the responses. The reliability of each construct was examined using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. All the items were found to be above the acceptance level. Table 3 represents the reliability test results

Constructs	Cronbach alpha	Number of items	Sample size
Ease of Use	0.92	2	260
Utility	0.88	1	260
Perceived benefits	0.89	2	260
Student Involvement	0.93	1	260
Self Efficacy beliefs	0.85	1	260
Job Satisfaction	0.95	2	260

Stepwise regression has been applied to find whether positive relationship is significant between the dependent variable Self efficacy belief and Job satisfaction and the considered independent variables: of ease of use (EU) , Utility (U), Perceived benefits

(PB). Stepwise regression is carried out to find the composite impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. This is done in several steps by adding new independent variables and regressing these with the dependent variables.

Table 4: Cronbach alpha and Pearson correlations for the evaluated constructs

Variables	Ease of Use	Utility	Perceived Benefits	Student Involvement	Self efficacy	Attitude towards technology	Computer usage efficacy	Cronbach Alpha
Ease of Use	1							.916
Utility	.774	1						.925
Perceived Benefits	.236*	.508**	1					.876
Student Involvement	.238*	.488**	.624**	1				.897
Self efficacy	.247*	.518**	.611**	.974**	1			.918
Attitude towards technology	.243*	.524**	.650**	.652**	.677**	1		.920
Computer usage efficacy	.279**	.395**	.513**	.309**	.353**	.353**	1	.918

The findings are split into two parts, the first of which provides for each assessed construct the reliability analyses (i.e., Pearson's correlations and Cronbach's alpha). The second component completes the testing of hypotheses and validates the research models proposed using univariate and multivariate general linear modeling. Because the data in this study is non-metric and observes simultaneous impacts, generalized linear modeling was the best approach. Generalized linear modeling is a flexible statistical model that includes normally distributed dependent variables and categorical or continuous independent variables. Table 4 presents the results of the Cronbach's alpha and Pearson correlations for the evaluated constructs. The Cronbach alpha was statistically acceptable for all the evaluated constructs, and the factor analysis showed that all the elements within each evaluated construct belong to and measure the same concept.

Validity:

Ho: Self-Efficacy beliefs & Job Satisfaction of teachers are positively related digital to their digital competencies. According to the Pearson correlations presented in Table 4, the relationship between Self Efficacy and Job Satisfaction ($r=.677$, $p<.000$) is significantly stronger. Teacher's attitudes toward using the technology thus supports the importance of the relationship between cognitive and affective responses in predicting users' technology acceptance. When Teachers self-assess their acceptance of technology, it is essential that they are used to specific technology to understand their self-efficacy, ease of use, utility, student involvement aspects while teaching. Teachers' technology self-efficacy is positively related to computer self-efficacy. In essence, the influence of computer and technology-specific perceptions, such as self-efficacy, might vary across different populations and technologies. Teacher's self-efficacy in the adjusted R square represents their perceived use and acceptance of technology. Constructions reported in the correlation analysis had positive, significant relationships ($p<.05$). All the designs in this study are statistically reliable. Initially, we evaluated the constructions separately to identify any differences. After careful analysis, there are no major differences between the self-efficacy and their acceptance to technology changes.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Study suggests that's self efficacy beliefs and Job satisfaction are related to each other. Teacher self efficacy is based upon the digital competence and technology acceptance.. the ease of use, utility and student involvement through enhanced learning enhance self efficacy beliefs of their own competencies resulting in better job satisfaction. The skill development should focus on digital competencies of teachers which is more important in the current scenario. The results presented here imply strongly that helping teachers develop their self-efficacy in digital competences is important, as studies show that teachers with a high self-efficacy are more likely to persist longer, provide a better teaching environment and not burn out as easily.

The study also provides some of the underpinnings crucial to addressing future in-service and pre-service teacher training and educational challenges. In particular we have identified some key areas which will require explicit attention. The results presented in this paper can also serve as a baseline for monitoring the development of teachers' self-efficacy over time as well as after particular training efforts. Future scope of research can also focus on comparing the digital competency and self-efficacy of teachers working for primary level education.

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